

Regimes in wet wollastonite carbonation: A comparative kinetics and multi-technique investigation

Sahra Homae^{a,b,c,*} , Doreen Ebert^a, Martin Rudolph^a

^a Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf, Helmholtz Institute Freiberg for Resource Technology, Freiberg, Germany

^b Technische Universität Dresden (TU Dresden), Dresden, Germany

^c HZDR Innovation GmbH, Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR), Dresden, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Calcium silicate minerals, including wollastonite, are considered promising feedstocks for mineral carbonation, particularly for applications in low-carbon building and construction materials; however, the mechanisms governing their behavior under mild wet carbonation conditions are not yet fully understood. While previous studies have primarily focused on enhancing carbonation through elevated temperatures, pressures, or chemical additives, the direct influence of operational conditions on reaction pathways and product evolution under additive-free mild conditions remains insufficiently explored. Here, two representative carbonated samples, exhibiting low (approximately 6%) and high (approximately 50%) carbonation efficiencies, were selected from a systematic screening for detailed analysis. These samples exemplify contrasting regimes of gas-liquid and solid-liquid mass transfer, primarily influenced by CO₂ flow rate and agitation speed. An integrated characterization strategy, incorporating XRF, TGA, XRD, BET, Pycnometry, and SEM-EDX, along with time-resolved kinetic model fitting, was employed. Phase and microstructural analyses reveal limited carbonate formation and sparse, discontinuous precipitates under mass-transfer-limited conditions, whereas extensive calcite precipitation and coalescing intergranular carbonate domains develop when mass transfer is enhanced. Variations in specific surface area, skeletal density, and thermal decomposition behavior correspond to progressive carbonate maturation during the reaction. Kinetic analysis of independent batch experiments at varying carbonation times indicates that both the Avrami model and the surface-reaction-controlled shrinking-core model provide the most suitable descriptions of the conversion data, suggesting that carbonation is mainly associated with surface-related dissolution, precipitation, and carbonate nucleation/growth. The diffusion-controlled shrinking-core model shows weaker agreement across the full reaction range, although transport limitations may become more relevant at later stages as carbonate-silica products develop. These findings provide a coherent mechanistic framework that links operational conditions to the evolution of reaction pathways during wet wollastonite carbonation under mild conditions.

1. Introduction

Mitigating anthropogenic CO₂ emissions remains a key challenge for industry and research. Technological strategies for mitigation generally encompass two main approaches: reducing CO₂ generation through methods such as fuel switching and efficiency improvements, and managing emitted CO₂ through carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) or carbon dioxide removal, with efforts concentrated on practical, affordable solutions especially in areas where CO₂ emission stems from other sources than fuel as in the case of cement production. Within

CCUS, mineral carbonation offers a durable method for fixing CO₂ by transforming Ca/Mg-bearing minerals or wastes (oxides, hydroxides, silicates) into thermodynamically stable carbonates, which can yield valuable byproducts [1,2].

A wide variety of feedstocks is suitable, including natural silicates (e.g., olivine, serpentine, wollastonite), mining residues, and industrial by-products (e.g., steel slag, cement fines). The choice of feedstock should match the intended end use (e.g., supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs), aggregates) to ensure proper performance and reduce downstream risks [1,3–5].

* Correspondence to: Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf, Helmholtz Institute Freiberg for Resource Technology, Chemnitz Str. 40, Freiberg 09599, Germany.

E-mail addresses: s.homae@hzdr.de (S. Homae), r.moeckel@hzdr.de (R. Möckel), d.ebert@hzdr.de (D. Ebert), m.rudolph@hzdr.de (M. Rudolph).

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The cement industry, one of the largest sources of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions, presents a particularly relevant application for mineral carbonation. Reducing emissions from the construction sector is critical to limiting global warming to below 1.5°C by the end of this century. The cement industry alone accounts for approximately 7% of global CO₂ emissions [6,7]. In 2019, the broader construction sector emitted about 9.95 Gt CO₂, making it the highest contributor to industrial emissions. Projections suggest a 16% reduction by 2030, with a net-zero target by 2050 [8]. Incorporating mineral carbonation into cement production could create a closed-loop process where captured CO₂ is mineralized and reused within the same supply chain, potentially leading to carbon-negative cement as standards and incentives develop [1,6]. Recent studies on carbonated magnesium slag and calcium bicarbonate-modified cement systems further show that carbonate-bearing materials can influence cement hydration, phase assemblage, and mechanical performance, supporting the relevance of mineral carbonation products for low-carbon construction materials [9, 10].

Within ex-situ mineral carbonation, both direct (additive-free) and indirect routes are employed, and the processes can be wet, dry, or semi-dry, depending on the feedstock and reactor design. In general, wet carbonation exhibits higher conversion efficiencies because water promotes CO₂ dissolution, ionic transport, and mineral dissolution. Similarly, recent reactive-transport studies in geological CO₂ storage have highlighted the important role of aqueous transport processes, wettability, and fluid-rock interactions in controlling CO₂ dissolution, mineralization, and long-term storage efficiency [11–15]. These observations emphasize the beneficial role of water in enhancing carbonation processes in both in-situ and ex-situ systems.

Although Ca/Mg silicates offer permanent CO₂ storage, their reaction kinetics are often slow under mild, direct conditions, and the relationships between operating conditions, reaction mechanisms, and carbonation rates remain insufficiently understood [1,16,17]. Selecting the most reactive mineral is therefore essential for advancing mineral carbonation research. Of the two main categories of silicate minerals, calcium silicates are more reactive. Among calcium silicate minerals, wollastonite (CaSiO₃) is recognized as one of the most reactive options in direct ex-situ wet carbonation systems [1,18]. This higher reactivity of wollastonite makes it particularly suitable for kinetic modeling and online process monitoring via spectroscopic methods, such as Raman spectroscopy, as it enables more precise observation of reaction pathways and opportunities for improvement. By beginning with the most reactive minerals, researchers can better model the kinetics, offering insights that could be integral to optimizing carbonation processes and enhancing scalability. In the next step, these basics can be applied to more complex systems, such as tailings [19,20].

The primary process occurs in two main steps: (1) leaching of Ca²⁺ from the wollastonite matrix into solution, and (2) nucleation and growth of CaCO₃ (calcium carbonate) from the dissolved calcium and carbonate ions [19,21,22]. Then, paying attention to these two main steps (1 and 3) is crucial to studying this reaction.

1. *Leaching:

2. CO₂ dissolution and (bi)carbonate species conversion:

3. *Nucleation and growth:

From a mechanistic perspective, previous studies indicate that the silica-rich rim initially forms via interfacial dissolution and

precipitation. In purely aqueous systems, the rim does not significantly hinder Ca²⁺ release, so reaction kinetics are predominantly governed by surface reactions. In contrast, in alkaline, saline, or supercritical CO₂ systems, the precipitation of additional carbonate or silicate phases can densify the rim and partially block it, shifting the overall kinetics toward diffusion control through the product layer. This transition is strongly influenced by system chemistry, water availability, and secondary phase formation characteristics [19,23,24]. Importantly, these coupled steps show why there is no universal “recipe” for speeding up wollastonite carbonation. Increasing the dissolution rate, whether by raising temperature or lowering pH to boost hydronium activity, indeed boosts Ca²⁺ release, but at the same time decreases dissolved carbonate availability because of lower CO₂ solubility at higher temperature or reduced carbonate speciation at lower pH. As a result, conditions that encourage Ca²⁺ leaching may suppress carbonate availability, and vice versa. This interplay emphasizes that the limiting steps can differ across studies and operating conditions. Therefore, systematically investigating various parameters and reaction environments is essential to identifying the dominant rate-limiting mechanism and developing optimized, process-specific carbonation strategies.

Although numerous studies investigate the influence of operating variables such as temperature, solid-to-liquid ratio, CO₂ delivery or pressure, and mixing on overall conversion, relatively few address how these factors alter the rate-controlling step or impact microstructural evolution [22,23,25].

Previous studies have examined wollastonite carbonation within a limited range of practical operating conditions, and most research focuses on elevated temperatures, pressure, or the use of additives (solution chemistry) to speed up the reaction. High temperature and pressure help speed up this process, similar to how various additives like acids (formic, acetic) and sodium bicarbonate are used [5,26–30]. All these factors that accelerate the process interfere with the actual and direct wollastonite wet carbonation, making it essential to first investigate this step to fully understand the main controlling parameters. With this foundational understanding, scientists can then develop better conditions to enhance the process. This study aims to address this need by mechanistically investigating the main operational factors identified from a systematic optimization screening of wollastonite wet carbonation under mild, additive-free conditions within a practical operating window. This includes evaluating the role of CO₂ flow rate, rotational speed, and solid-to-liquid ratio, and comparing selected low- and high-conversion conditions that represent different apparent mass-transfer regimes. The objective is to establish a comprehensive understanding of these factors and their effects on microstructural evolution and kinetic behavior for practical applications. This experimental study begins with an initial screening phase to define practical operating ranges and choose two conditions for a detailed study, giving a clear basis for the samples used. Research on mild, additive-free wet carbonation of wollastonite is still limited, and studies that focus on the reaction mechanism under these mild conditions are rare. To fill this gap, we use several characterization methods (X-ray Fluorescence (XRF), Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA), X-ray Diffraction (XRD), Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET), and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)) and test different linearized kinetic models. We include models like the Avrami framework and the shrinking-core (surface-reaction and diffusion-controlled) approach because they are well-suited to describe Ca-leaching and the formation of carbonate product layers during Ca-silicate carbonation.

We chose these characterization methods because they each offer different insights into the microstructural changes that drive the reaction. As mentioned earlier, aqueous wollastonite carbonation has two main rate-controlling steps: first, Ca²⁺ leaches from the silicate structure, and second, the calcium carbonate product layer forms and grows. XRF, TGA and XRD help identify the elements, and phases in both intermediate and final products, while BET and SEM shows changes in surface area and shape, which are important for understanding how the material

dissolves and how the product layer develops. By combining these analytical and kinetic approaches, we can connect microstructural changes to reaction mechanisms and develop useful guidelines for using CO₂ in cement processes.

2. Materials and methods

The main material used in this study is natural wollastonite (Töpfereibedarf Lehrer GesmbH, Austria). XRF analysis indicated that the sample matched typical wollastonite compositions. The raw material was used as received, without further purification. Prior to carbonation experiments, the feedstock was characterized to establish its baseline chemical, mineralogical, and physical properties. More details are in the section #3.1.

2.1. Analytical instruments and purposes

Several analytical techniques were used to characterize the chemical, structural, and physical properties of wollastonite before and after carbonation. Elemental composition was determined by wavelength-dispersive X-ray fluorescence analysis (WD-XRF) using a PANalytical AxiosMAX spectrometer equipped with an Rh anode, operated with SuperQ5 software. Samples were analyzed as fused glass beads following the calibrated wide-range oxide program (Wroxi; 25–60 kV, 66–160 mA). Prior to fusion, powders were ground to < 63 μm using a Retsch disc mill (tungsten carbide pot). Samples were dried overnight at 105°C, then annealed for 2 h at 950°C to determine loss on ignition (LOI). For bead preparation, 1.125 g of annealed sample was mixed with 9.0 g Li₂B₄O₇ flux (≈1:8) in a Pt crucible and fused at 1050°C using a Claisse TheOx Advanced melting furnace. Crystalline phases were identified by powder XRD using a PANalytical Empyrean diffractometer with a Co X-ray tube (35 kV, 35 mA), Fe Kβ-filter, and a PIXcel3D (Medipix3 1 × 1) area detector. Patterns were collected from 5°– 80° (2θ) with a step size of 0.0131° (irradiated area 15 mm × 12 mm, total acquisition time 153 min). Qualitative phase identification was performed in PANalytical HighScore (3.0.4) using the ICDD PDF–5 + (2025) database. Quantitative phase analysis was obtained by Rietveld refinement using Profex(5.1.0) [31]. The data obtained from Rietveld refinement are perfectly consistent with results from other techniques, such as XRF. However, these results require careful evaluation because standard micronization, typically performed using a Retsch McCrone mill, was not feasible due to the potential alteration of the carbonated samples. Consequently, additional sample treatment was minimized.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was used to quantify the natural CO₂ content and to determine the total CO₂ uptake following carbonation. Measurements were performed using a NETZSCH TG 309 Libra Classic under a nitrogen atmosphere, with a heating rate of 20 K·min⁻¹ from 30°C to 1000°C. Particle size distribution was evaluated with laser diffraction (Sympatec HELOS, Germany). Surface properties were assessed through Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) nitrogen adsorption to determine the specific surface area (SSA) using a Micromeritics Gemini VII 2390 t analyzer (Gemini VII software 5.00), following DIN ISO 9277:2022. Prior to analysis, samples were degassed at 200°C for 3 h under flowing nitrogen gas; measurements were performed with nitrogen gas as the adsorptive gas using an equilibration time of 5 s, and skeletal density was measured by helium gas pycnometry using an AccuPyc II 1340 pycnometer (V2.01; serial no. 3356), following DIN 66137–2. Measurements were performed with helium gas as the analysis gas, using an equilibrium rate of 0.005 psig·min⁻¹ and 20 purge cycles prior to analysis (sample mass ~11.72 g; chamber insert 35 cm³; cell volume 39.6119 cm³). Microstructural features, including particle morphology, dissolution textures, and carbonate precipitation, were examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Samples were carbon-coated using a Leica EM MED020 carbon coater prior to analysis. SEM and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) analyses were performed using a FEI Quanta 650 FEG field-emission gun scanning

electron microscope equipped with two Bruker Quantax X-Flash 5030 energy dispersive X-ray spectrometers (EDX). The instrument was operated at an accelerating voltage of 15 kV, and a working distance of approximately 13 mm. Elemental maps were acquired using Bruker Esprit software.

These techniques collectively enable the evaluation of compositional changes, phase evolution, surface modification, and morphological development associated with the carbonation process.

2.2. Experimental setup and procedure

This section explains the study's methodology, covering the investigation of wet carbonation reaction mechanisms under specific conditions. It details the main experimental design, sample selection strategy, the kinetic study procedure, and the determination of CO₂ uptake.

2.2.1. Main experimental design for carbonation and samples selection

The experiments were conducted at atmospheric pressure using a reflux setup/ Batch reactor, which include a three-necked reactor fitted with a condenser, thermometer, and magnetic stirrer-heater. A pressurized CO₂ cylinder provided the pure CO₂ source, with flow rate regulated by a flowmeter (Fig. 1).

Before carbonation, wollastonite was ground using a disc mill (Retsch RS 200, Germany) for 10 min. After the system reached the target temperature and the CO₂ flow was stabilized, the wollastonite was added according to the specified solid-to-liquid ratio (S/L) (Table 1). The reaction time was fixed at 2 h. Following carbonation, the slurry was dried at 105°C for 12 h before further analysis.

2.2.2. Sample selection

A structured design-of-experiments (DOE) screening was conducted to map the mild wet carbonation space for Wollastonite, considering factors such as solid-to-liquid ratio (S/L), temperature (T), agitation speed (min⁻¹), and CO₂ flow rate. The complete DOE dataset has been made openly available through RODARE [32,33], while the present work focuses specifically on the mechanistic interpretation of two representative carbonation conditions selected from the screening study. Based on DOE responses, specifically normalized CO₂ uptake obtained from thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), two representative conditions were selected for the mechanistic study: i.e. the highest carbonated (optimum) and the lowest carbonated conditions. These selected conditions were subsequently rerun for use in this study. The selected samples and their operating conditions are summarized in Table 1. The least carbonated sample is compared with other sample that vary in solid-to-liquid ratio, rotational speed, and CO₂ flow rate. As

Fig. 1. Experimental reflux setup used for additive-free wollastonite wet carbonation. The system consists of a three-necked glass reactor equipped with a condenser, thermometer, CO₂ inlet, magnetic heater–stirrer, water bath, and mass-flow meter for controlling the supplied CO₂ flow.

Table 1

Selected operating conditions for the representative low- and high-carbonation wollastonite samples used in the mechanistic study. The samples were selected from the DOE screening based on normalized CO₂ uptake determined by TGA and were subsequently reproduced under the listed conditions for detailed characterization.

Run	T (°C)	S/l (%)	CO ₂ flow (mL min ⁻¹)	Rotational speed (min ⁻¹)	CO ₂ Uptake (%)
Lowest	90	30	100	300	1.95
Highest	90	10	700	900	15.29

phase changes are the primary indicator for monitoring mineral carbonation, Table 3 provides a quantitative representation of all potential carbonatable phases and their transformations under these conditions.

2.2.3. Kinetics experiments protocol

The kinetics study employed the optimal condition identified in the previous Design of Experiments (DOE) screening, specifically the condition yielding the highest carbonation degree. The wet carbonation process was replicated under identical operating conditions with varying reaction times. Based on the DOE, which indicated an optimum at approximately 120 min, a non-uniform time schedule was implemented (0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 45, 60, 75, 90, 120, 150, and 180) min to elucidate early-time kinetics, incorporate the 120-minute optimum, and verify the plateau or passivation phase. To maintain consistent solid-liquid ratios, hydrodynamic conditions, and gas-liquid interactions, separate batch experiments were conducted for each time point and the reaction was stopped at the predetermined endpoint, totaling 12 runs. This approach prevented artifacts such as volume loss, sediment-liquid drift, CO₂ depletion, or temperature disturbances. All final products were dried for 12 h at 105°C, with phase changes assessed by XRD and CO₂ uptake measured by TGA.

To identify the most suitable kinetic model, the integral (linearized) fitting approach was employed. The linearized forms of the candidate models were plotted using the transformed conversion time data, and the kinetic parameters were obtained from linear regression. Model suitability was evaluated using the coefficient of determination (R²), adjusted R², residual sum of squares (RSS), root mean square error (RMSE) Table 6, and residual plots calculated in the corresponding transformed coordinate space.

2.3. Determination of CO₂ uptake

CO₂ uptake (theoretical and experimental).

Theoretical CO₂ uptake was estimated from bulk chemistry using XRF, under the assumption that only CaO and MgO undergo carbonation as described in the following reactions (1,2).

For a 1 g sample with Z % (m/m) CaO and Y % (m/m) MgO, the potential CO₂ gain is calculated as follows

$$\begin{aligned} Z\% \left(\frac{m}{m} \right) \text{CaO} &\times \frac{1 \text{ mol CaO}}{56.07 \text{ g CaO}} \times \frac{1 \text{ mol CO}_2}{1 \text{ mol CaO}} \times \frac{44 \text{ g CO}_2}{1 \text{ mol CO}_2} \\ &= Z\% \times 0.78 \text{ CO}_2 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} Y\% \left(\frac{m}{m} \right) \text{MgO} &\times \frac{1 \text{ mol MgO}}{40.3 \text{ g MgO}} \times \frac{1 \text{ mol CO}_2}{1 \text{ mol MgO}} \times \frac{44 \text{ g CO}_2}{1 \text{ mol CO}_2} \\ &= Y\% \times 1.1 \text{ CO}_2 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{CO}_2^{\text{theoretical}}(\%) = 0.78 Z\% + 1.1 Y\% \quad (5)$$

For comparison as mass percent, this value was corrected to account

for native carbonate content as measured by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

$$\text{Theoretical CO}_2 \text{ Uptake } (\%) = (0.78 \cdot Z\% + 1.1 \cdot Y\%) - \text{Natural CO}_2 (\%) \quad (6)$$

Therefore, based on the XRF and natural CO₂ uptake measured by TGA, after this calculation, since the CaO and MgO in the wollastonite sample were reported as Z = 42.9%(m/m) and Y = 1.6%(m/m) (XRF based) and Natural CO₂ was 3.34% (TGA based), the theoretical CO₂ uptake is 31.8%.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Theoretical CO}_2 \text{ Uptake } \% &= (0.78 \cdot (42.9\%) + 1.1 \cdot (1.6\%)) - 3.34\% \\ &= 31.8\% \end{aligned} \quad (6-a)$$

Experimental CO₂ Uptake quantified the net amount of CO₂ sequestered in the solid as a result of carbonation. To isolate CO₂ fixed during the reaction, the CO₂ content originally present in the feed material was subtracted from that measured in the carbonated sample.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) determined CO₂ content by measuring mass loss associated with carbonate decomposition in the 500°C – 900°C temperature range. This interval was chosen because it predominantly corresponds to CO₂ release from carbonate phases. To compare samples with varying total mass losses, the carbonate-related mass loss was normalized by the total mass loss measured between 30°C and 975°C, representing the effective solid mass after removal of moisture.

Accordingly, CO₂ uptake was calculated as the difference between the normalized carbonate mass loss of the carbonated sample and that of the feed, with the result rescaled to the initial sample mass. This procedure ensures that the reported CO₂ uptake reflects only the net CO₂ sequestered by carbonation, excluding contributions from pre-existing carbonates in the feed material.

The final normalized CO₂ uptake is calculated as the difference between the feed and carbonated sample states (this method was used and described before in [34]):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{CO}_2 \text{ Uptake } \% &= \left(\frac{\Delta m_{\text{Carb},500-900}}{100 - \Delta m_{\text{Carb},30-975}} - \frac{\Delta m_{\text{Feed},500-900}}{100 - \Delta m_{\text{Feed},30-975}} \right) \\ &\times \frac{100 - \Delta m_{\text{Feed},30-975}}{100} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta m_{s,500-900} = m_{s,500^\circ\text{C}} - m_{s,900^\circ\text{C}} \quad (7-a)$$

$$\Delta m_{s,30-975} = m_{s,30^\circ\text{C}} - m_{s,975^\circ\text{C}} \quad (7-b)$$

Where *s* denotes the sample state, with *s* = Carb for the carbonated sample and *s* = Feed for the uncarbonated material, Δ*m*_{*s*,500–900} represents the mass loss associated with carbonate decomposition (CO₂ release) and Δ*m*_{*s*,30–975} corresponds to the total mass loss used for normalization.

For kinetic analysis, the conversion extent *X* was determined by dividing the experimental CO₂ uptake by the maximum theoretical CO₂ uptake.

$$X = \frac{\text{CO}_2 \text{ uptake}}{\text{maximum theoretical CO}_2 \text{ uptake}}$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of the feedstock (Raw wollastonite)

The raw wollastonite was characterized to establish baseline chemical, mineralogical, and physical properties prior to carbonation. XRF analysis confirmed a Ca–Si composition typical of wollastonite, with key oxide components as listed in Table 2. XRD analysis verified wollastonite as the dominant crystalline phase, accompanied by minor phases such as Calcite (c.f. Table 3). The particle size distribution obtained by laser diffraction resulted in the size weight balanced quantiles (10%, 50% and

Table 2

Chemical composition of the feed sample (XRF).

Oxide	SiO ₂	CaO	TiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	Mn ₂ O ₄	MgO	K ₂ O
% (m/m)	51.76	42.91	0.02	0.27	0.38	0.05	1.6	0.03

Table 3

Mineralogical composition of the feed sample, determined by quantitative X-ray diffraction (QXRD). Phase contents are reported in % (m/m) together with the corresponding estimated standard error derived from the Rietveld refinement.

Phase	Chemical Formula	% (m/m)
Wollastonite	CaSiO ₃	75.5 ± 1.7
Calcite	CaCO ₃	8.3 ± 0.3
Quartz	SiO ₂	8.4 ± 0.2
Pyroxene	CaMgSi ₂ O ₆	7.9 ± 0.3

90%) and Sauter mean diameter (ST) as in Table 4. BET measurements provided an initial specific surface area of 4.67 m²·g⁻¹, while gas pycnometry determined the skeletal density to be 2.893 g·cm⁻³ (c.f. Table 5). SEM imaging revealed elongated, bladed particles typical of wollastonite, serving as a microstructural reference for comparison with selected carbonated samples (c.f. Fig. 3).

3.2. Carbonation degree and phase identification

Quantitative X-Ray Diffraction (QXRD) was employed to compare the phase assemblage of the feed with two selected carbonated samples representing the lowest and highest CO₂ uptake (Fig. 2 - a). The feed is dominated by wollastonite (75.5% (m/m)), with minor amounts of calcite (8.3% (m/m)), quartz (8.4% (m/m)), and pyroxene (7.9% (m/m)). After carbonation, the relative wollastonite content decreases while calcite increases, confirming that CaCO₃ is the main reaction product and that the degree of carbonation differs between the two selected conditions.

In the lowest-uptake sample, wollastonite remains the major phase (67.8% (m/m)), while calcite increases moderately to 13.2% (m/m), indicating limited conversion. In contrast, the highest-uptake sample exhibits a pronounced increase in calcite (49.8% (m/m)) and a substantial decrease in wollastonite (33.8% (m/m)), consistent with a significantly higher conversion. The contents of quartz and pyroxene remain comparatively low (approximately 7.8% (m/m) – 8.6% (m/m)) and do not follow the same trend as wollastonite and calcite, suggesting that these phases are largely inert under the applied carbonation conditions and primarily reflect the mineralogical background of the feed.

Also, this phase analysis of selected samples shows a clear increase in apparent calcite crystallite size, progressing from the feed to the low-uptake product and then to the high-uptake product (Fig. 2 - b). This trend suggests progressive calcite crystallite growth and improved crystallinity as carbonation advances and conversion increases. The feed sample exhibits the smallest apparent crystallite size, while both carbonated samples display substantially larger values. The high-uptake sample shows the largest apparent calcite crystallite size, suggesting more extensive carbonate development under conditions expected to provide improved mass transfer and CO₂ availability. In addition, the apparent calcite crystallite size increases from the low-uptake to the high-uptake sample, indicating more developed carbonate domains

Table 4

PSD of Raw wollastonite.

Parameter	Value
$d_{10,3}$	0.8 μm
$d_{50,3}$	4.2 μm
$d_{90,3}$	24.0 μm
d_{ST}	2.2 μm

Table 5Physical properties of the feed and selected carbonated wollastonite samples. Skeletal density was determined by pycnometry and BET surface area was determined from N₂ adsorption measurements. Values are reported as mean ± 95% confidence interval, based on duplicate measurements for BET surface area and 40 measurements for pycnometry.

	Sample Density g·cm ⁻³	BET Surface Area m ² ·g ⁻¹
Feed	2.893 ± 0.001	4.67 ± 0.15
Lowest	2.895 ± 0.001	3.06 ± 0.20
Highest	2.723 ± 0.002	4.29 ± 0.20

under high-uptake operating conditions. This trend aligns with the distinct process parameters of the high-uptake regime, characterized by higher agitation speed, increased CO₂ flow rate, and a lower solid-to-liquid (S/L) ratio, which are expected to improve hydrodynamics and CO₂ availability, thereby supporting more extensive carbonate precipitation and apparent crystallite growth. In contrast, the low-uptake regime, with lower agitation speed, reduced CO₂ flow rate, and a higher S/L ratio, is consistent with more restricted transport conditions and encourages localized precipitation with restricted growth. This evolution in crystallite size is consistent with the trends observed in the BET and TGA/DTG datasets, which are examined in detail in subsequent sections.

The kinetics study shows a clear, time-dependent trend in both phase assemblage and carbonate development as a function of carbonation duration. QXRD analysis (Fig. 2 - c) reveals a gradual increase in calcite content with reaction time, accompanied by a corresponding decrease in the wollastonite phase, supporting ongoing conversion via wollastonite dissolution and CaCO₃ precipitation. In contrast, the other phases, such as quartz and pyroxene, remain nearly constant throughout the experiment, indicating that the primary changes result from wollastonite consumption and carbonate formation rather than the transformation of minor silicate phases. Additionally, the apparent calcite crystallite size (Fig. 2 - d), as determined by XRD peak broadening, increases from approximately 90 nm at early reaction times to 150 nm – 160 nm at 180 min, reflecting progressive crystal growth and improved crystallinity of the carbonate product as carbonation advances. It is important to note that the reported crystallite size values are provided for comparative purposes only, as the powders were not micronized prior to XRD analysis, and particle-size heterogeneity or preferred orientation may affect peak profiles and impact the true crystallite size values. However, consistent application of the fitting protocol across the entire time series supports the interpretation that extended carbonation duration enhances both calcite yield and the formation of larger, more developed calcite crystallites. These kinds of observations, such as increasing calcite crystallite size over time and during carbonation, associated with parameters like increased CO₂ flow rate and temperature, have been reported in some studies to contribute to cement and building materials carbonation [35,36].

3.3. Morphological changes under low and high uptake conditions

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images show carbonate particles on silicate grains exhibiting a rhombohedral morphology, which is consistent with calcite. Elemental mapping corroborates this identification: calcium-rich domains align with the rhombohedral features, while silicon-rich regions correspond to the underlying wollastonite matrix [22,23,37]. In the feed sample (Fig. 3 - a,b), no rhombohedral carbonate crystals were detected despite targeted examination. The low-uptake product (Fig. 3-c,d) displays scattered rhombohedral, forming a thin, discontinuous film. In contrast, the high-uptake product (Fig. 3 - e, f) contains abundant and locally coalesced rhombohedral particles, resulting in a denser product layer and partial bridging

Fig. 2. Quantitative XRD phase composition and calcite crystallite size evolution during wollastonite carbonation. **(a)** Quantitative phase composition of the feed, low-carbonated (~6% carbonation efficiency), and high-carbonated (~50% carbonation efficiency) samples. **(b)** Corresponding calcite crystallite sizes determined for the feed and selected carbonated samples. **(c)** Quantitative phase composition as a function of carbonation time during the kinetic study. **(d)** Evolution of calcite crystallite size with carbonation duration, showing progressive crystal growth as carbonation proceeds. Error bars in the phase analysis represent estimated standard errors, reported as $\pm 3\sigma$, from the QXRD refinement. Error bars for crystallite size correspond to the uncertainty values obtained from the XRD peak-profile/crystallite-size fitting output.

between grains. These findings indicate a larger areal coverage of calcite in the high-uptake sample compared to the low-uptake sample. In the EDX mapping (Fig. 3, g), the displayed colors are software-assigned overlays, with red and green indicating the relative X-ray intensities of Ca and Si at each pixel, respectively. Areas enriched in Ca (high Ca/Si ratio) are attributed to CaCO₃ precipitates (calcite), while regions enriched in Si (low Ca/Si ratio) correspond to the silicate matrix (wollastonite/CaSiO₃). The map shows that Ca-rich, reddish crystals are distributed on and locally coat the Si-rich, greenish wollastonite grain, suggesting that calcite formed as a secondary precipitate on the wollastonite surface during carbonation. These observations are also reported in other studies under different conditions, such as high CO₂ partial pressure, additives, or accelerators [21,23,27]. Spectra acquired from representative points or areas in these regions demonstrate that elemental peak heights directly correspond to the map colors (c.f. Figs. 3 - g1, g2). The reddish crystals produce spectra dominated by Ca (and O) with relatively weak Si signals, whereas the greenish grain surface displays a stronger Si signal along with Ca and O, consistent with the underlying wollastonite or silicate phase.

3.4. Microstructural evolution, surface passivation, and the role of mass transport

The distinct outcomes observed under high and low-uptake carbonation conditions underscore the importance of mixing efficiency, CO₂ availability, and the solid-to-liquid (S/L) ratio in controlling reaction kinetics and microstructural evolution during wollastonite carbonation. Both experiments used the same feed particle-size

distribution; thus, differences between the resulting products are attributed to condition-dependent changes during carbonation rather than initial particle size. Notably, carbonation reduces the BET specific surface area (SSA) (Table 5) relative to the feed in both cases: the feed exhibits 4.67 m².g⁻¹, the low-uptake product decreases to 3.06 m².g⁻¹, and the high-uptake product reaches 4.29 m².g⁻¹. This reduction in SSA indicates that carbonation generally results in partial loss of accessible surface, consistent with product-layer coverage, pore-mouth occlusion, and/or particle agglomeration. In the high-uptake regime (90 min⁻¹, 10% S/L, 700 mL.min⁻¹ CO₂), vigorous mixing and high CO₂ supply promote efficient slurry circulation, frequent renewal of reactive surfaces, and sustained supersaturation with respect to CaCO₃. These conditions are expected to promote higher carbonation degrees and favor more distributed precipitation throughout the system. Although the SSA of the high-uptake product remains lower than that of the feed, it is relatively higher than the low-uptake product, suggesting that favorable hydrodynamics may mitigate surface blocking by limiting severe agglomeration and preserving a more open surface microstructure. Under these conditions, increased CO₂ availability and vigorous mixing are expected to sustain reactant supply and continuous surface renewal, which may promote a higher density of carbonate nuclei and a more uniform distribution of precipitates during the initial stages. As carbonation advances, the sustained supply of reactants is consistent with continued crystal growth, in agreement with the larger apparent calcite crystallite size (see section 3.2) observed in the highest-carbonated sample compared to the lowest-carbonated sample. Therefore, the high-uptake regime supports both extensive carbonate formation and the development of more mature calcite domains, while

Fig. 3. SEM micrographs illustrating the morphological evolution of wollastonite during wet carbonation. (a,b) Feed wollastonite at low and high magnification, respectively. (c,d) Low-carbonated sample (~6% carbonation efficiency) showing the initial formation of carbonate precipitates on the wollastonite surface. (e,f) High-carbonated sample (~50% carbonation efficiency) exhibiting extensive calcite precipitation and the development of intergranular carbonate domains. (g) SEM-EDS elemental map of a representative carbonated particle, highlighting the distribution of Ca and Si. (g.1) EDS spectrum collected from the carbonate-rich rhombohedral crystal region, confirming Ca-rich carbonate precipitation. (g.2) EDS spectrum collected from the wollastonite substrate, showing the characteristic Ca-Si composition of the parent mineral.

maintaining a higher accessible surface.

Conversely, the low-uptake condition (300 min⁻¹, 30% S/L, 100 mL min⁻¹ CO₂) is characterized by a reduced mixing intensity and limited CO₂ transport, which lower supersaturation and slow the renewal of reactive surfaces. Under these conditions, carbonation is more likely to initiate at heterogeneous nucleation sites such as silicate edges, defects, or residual calcite. As a result, carbonate formation remains discontinuous and does not develop into a well-defined porous product layer. This interpretation aligns with the XRD line-broadening results, which show a smaller apparent calcite crystallite size (See section 3.2) in the lowest-carbonated sample compared to the highest-carbonated sample. These findings suggest limited crystal development or increased defect density when supersaturation and reactant supply are inadequate to support sustained growth.

Collectively, these findings suggest that the precipitation pathway and resulting product architecture, are influenced by hydrodynamics, CO₂ supply, and S/L ratio, and that these factors are associated with changes in accessible surface area and the extent of surface blocking during wollastonite carbonation. Favorable mass-transfer conditions are consistent with more distributed precipitation and a less blocked microstructure, while suboptimal conditions appear to favor localized precipitation, agglomeration, and early surface blocking, resulting in a pronounced loss of accessible surface area.

These mechanistic interpretations, consistent with findings reported in the broader literature. [35], demonstrated that localized calcite precipitation can substantially alter pore geometry and reduce accessible reactivity, even at moderate reaction degrees. Additionally, [35,36] established that grain-coating and pore-filling precipitation modes have markedly different effects on permeability and porosity. In [36] it was reported that supersaturation and CO₂ supply significantly influence carbonate precipitation pathways and resulting surface properties. These results suggest that optimizing hydrodynamic and mass-transport conditions can help preserve reactive surface exposure and reduce passivation during wollastonite carbonation, leading to higher degrees of carbonation.

3.5. Density and surface area changes linked to phase replacement

The skeletal density of the raw wollastonite lies within the typical range for CaSiO₃ (2.86 g.cm⁻³ – 3.09 g.cm⁻³) [38], with the feed sample measured at 2.893 g.cm⁻³ and a BET surface area of 4.67 m².g⁻¹. Under low-uptake conditions, the density remains nearly unchanged at 2.895 g.cm⁻³, whereas the BET surface area decreases substantially to 3.06 m².g⁻¹ (Table 5). This pairing of consistent density with reduced SSA is consistent with limited phase transformation and suggests that the extent of phase replacement remained relatively low under these conditions. This baseline provides a useful reference for assessing the progression of mineral transformation with increasing carbonation degree. In the high-uptake sample, the density decreases markedly to 2.723 g.cm⁻³, consistent with partial replacement of wollastonite (≈ 2.90 g.cm⁻³) by lower-density calcite (≈ 2.71 g.cm⁻³) [39] and amorphous Si-rich phases (≈ 2.1 g.cm⁻³ – 2.3 g.cm⁻³). This observation is consistent with carbonation progressing beyond simple surface coating and suggests more extensive mineral transformation. The BET surface area also increases relative to the low-uptake product (4.29 m².g⁻¹) but remains lower than the feed. This intermediate SSA may result from the competing effects of (i) partial pore occlusion and surface smoothing during carbonation and (ii) the formation of a more porous carbonate-silica product coupled with mechanical surface renewal under higher shear. The increase in SSA might also be attributed to the nanoscale porosity formation within the amorphous silica networks, suggesting that these microstructural changes could be a pathway for future detailed microscopy-based exploration.

3.6. Thermal decomposition behavior of carbonated products (TGA/DTG)

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of the two different carbonation regimes in uptake level, compared under an inert atmosphere (N₂) (Fig. 4) shows that CO₂ release from carbonated calcium silicate systems typically occurs in the high-temperature decarbonation region (approximately 600°C - 800°C) [40–43], where CaCO₃ decomposes to CaO and CO₂. Mass loss observed below 200°C is generally assigned to the removal of physically adsorbed water and the dehydration of hydrated reaction products (e.g., Ca-modified silica gel), rather than carbonate decomposition [43]. In the carbonated silicate system, other kinds of calcium carbonate, metastable calcium carbonates, like aragonite and vaterite, could exist, as many studies show they might be decomposed in lower temperature regions, approximately 400°C – 600°C [43–45] while the more stable or well-crystalline form of calcium carbonate, Calcite, decomposes at approximately 600°C - 800°C. In these measurements, both the lowest- and highest-carbonated samples exhibit a distinct mass-loss step within this interval, confirming that the absorbed CO₂ is predominantly stored in carbonate, specifically calcite.

Although both DTG maxima occur within the calcite decarbonation region, the temperature of maximum CO₂ release differs: the lowest-carbonated sample peaks at 742.3°C, while the highest-carbonated sample peaks at 770.3°C. Such shifts for the same carbonate phase can arise because the apparent decomposition temperature is sensitive to carbonate crystallinity, defect density, and microstructural confinement, as reported in previous studies regarding increasing crystallinity and carbonate “maturation” [43,46–48]. The earlier, lower-temperature DTG maximum in the lowest-carbonated sample aligns with limited carbonation, where carbonate is mainly present as sparse, thin, or defect-rich precipitates that decarbonate more readily. This interpretation is supported by XRD line-broadening, which indicates a smaller apparent calcite crystallite size in the lowest-carbonated sample, is consistent with less-developed carbonate domains. In contrast, the highest-carbonated sample contains a larger carbonate fraction and a more developed assemblage, with a correspondingly larger apparent calcite crystallite size. This is consistent with more mature calcite domains or carbonate formed within a thicker carbonate-silica product layer, which can delay CO₂ release to higher temperatures.

DTG behavior can be discussed in relation to the applied carbonation conditions (Table 1). Although both experiments were conducted at 90°C, the highest-uptake condition (900 min⁻¹, S/L = 10%, 700 mL.min⁻¹ CO₂) is expected to provide improved gas-liquid mass transfer and surface renewal, sustaining supersaturation and enabling continued precipitation and carbonate development, as reflected by the

Fig. 4. DTG curves of the two selected carbonated samples measured under N₂ (20 mL.min⁻¹) from 30°C to 1000°C (20 K.min⁻¹). The main decarbonation reaction occurs at ~650°C–850°C, with T(DTG_{max}) at 742.3°C (lowest uptake) and 770.3°C (highest uptake).

higher $T(\text{DTG}_{\text{max}})$ (770.3°C). In contrast, the lowest-uptake condition (300 min⁻¹, S/L = 30%, 100 mL.min⁻¹ CO₂) is consistent with more restricted CO₂ availability and renewal of the mineral-fluid interface, leading to localized and discontinuous precipitation and less-developed carbonate that releases CO₂ at a lower $T(\text{DTG}_{\text{max}})$ (742.3°C). Thus, the shift in CO₂-release temperature is interpreted as being associated not only with carbonate presence but also with the influence of hydrodynamics and CO₂ supply on carbonate abundance, crystallite development, and the degree of confinement within the reaction products.

Regarding carbonation duration, the kinetics study shows a progressive increase in the $T(\text{DTG}_{\text{max}})$ with increasing time (Fig. 5), observed under the highest-uptake condition, indicating that the CO₂-bearing carbonate phase evolves during the reaction. This trend is consistent with carbonate maturation, including increasing crystallinity and coherent domain size, possible transformation of less stable carbonate environments toward calcite, and greater confinement of carbonate within a growing carbonate-silica product layer. Collectively, these effects may increase the apparent thermal stability of stored CO₂ and shift the maximum CO₂ release rate to higher temperatures as carbonation progresses.

In Fig. 5 this difference in decomposition temperatures is more apparent when focusing on the longest and shortest carbonation times. The decomposition temperature for the shortest time is around 746.2°C, and for the longest time it is about 776°C. Fig. 5 shows this temperature for all the samples with different carbonation durations, which follow the same trend. Other works [36] also reported that, with increasing reaction time, the formed calcite crystals are better defined and thermodynamically more stable, which is why they might decompose at higher temperatures. This trend also correlates with the calcite crystallite-size evolution discussed in section 3.2. As carbonation time increases, calcite crystals grow and become more mature, which may increase their apparent thermal stability and therefore shift the decomposition ($T(\text{DTG}_{\text{max}})$) temperature to higher values. While wollastonite is representative, other silicates may exhibit distinct maturation kinetics.

3.7. Kinetics model fitting

Wollastonite was selected for the kinetics study of wet carbonation under mild conditions due to its higher reactivity compared to other common minerals. This increased reactivity may result from differences in silica gel formation behavior or from its specific chemical composition relative to magnesium silicate (Mg-Si) minerals [1,18]. Specifically for this study, the carbonation condition corresponding to the high uptake

carbonated wollastonite sample was chosen, as mentioned in section 2.2.3.

The experimental conversion data were evaluated using three kinetic models: the shrinking-core model (SCM_{surface reaction}) with chemical surface-reaction control, the SCM with diffusion control through a product layer (SCM_{diffusion}) [49,50] and the Avrami (Johnson-Mehl-Avrami-Kolmogorov JMAK) model [50,51].

According to the shrinking-core model (SCM), when the process is governed by a chemical reaction at the particle surface or by diffusion through the product layer, the corresponding kinetic expressions are provided by Eqs. (8) and (9), respectively.

$$1 - (1 - X)^{1/3} = k_s \cdot t \quad (8)$$

$$1 - 3(1 - X)^{2/3} + 2(1 - X) = k_d \cdot t \quad (9)$$

where k_s and k_d are the apparent rate constants for the chemical surface reaction-controlled and diffusion-controlled mechanisms, respectively; X is the carbonation conversion, expressed based on CO₂ uptake; and t is the reaction time.

The Avrami model, which is widely used to describe time-dependent transformation processes involving nucleation and growth, relates the extent of reaction to time according to:

$$X = 1 - e^{(-k_A t^n)} \quad (10)$$

The linear form of the Avrami equation can be expressed as:

$$\ln[-\ln(1 - X)] = \ln k_A + n \ln t \quad (11)$$

where k_A is the reaction rate constant, and n is the Avrami exponent, which indicates the nature of the transformation process.

The fitted parameters and goodness-of-fit metrics are summarized in Table 6, while the transformed dataset used for the linearized fitting is provided in Table S1. Based on the combined evaluation of R², adjusted R², RSS, RMSE, and residual distributions (Fig. 6 - d,e), the Avrami and SCM surface-reaction models provide the most suitable descriptions of the experimental data, suggesting that carbonation is governed primarily by surface-related processes over most of the reaction progress. The Avrami exponent determined in this study ($n = 0.993$) is a strong indicator of a first-order kinetic process. In solid-state kinetics, ($n \sim 1$) typically corresponds to an interface-controlled mechanism or to one-dimensional growth, which aligns well with the superior fit of the SCM_{surface reaction} model. In contrast, the SCM_{diffusion} model shows weaker agreement over the full reaction range and a less favorable residual distribution (Fig. 6 - c,e). Additional nonlinear fitting results are provided in the Supporting Information (Figure S1 and Table S2, Table S3)

Fig. 5. DTG-based evaluation of carbonate thermal behavior during time-resolved wollastonite carbonation. (a) Overlay of DTG curves for samples collected at different carbonation times, showing the evolution of the main calcite decarbonation peak. (b) Extracted $T(\text{DTG}_{\text{max}})$ of the calcite decomposition peak as a function of carbonation time is used to illustrate the trend toward higher decomposition temperatures with increasing carbonation duration.

Table 6

Linearized kinetic fitting results with regression uncertainties for the Avrami, SCM surface-reaction, and SCM diffusion models. The \pm values represent 95% confidence intervals for the regression slope and intercept models.

Model	Linearized equation	Regression equation	Extracted parameter (s)	R ²	Adjusted R ²	RSS	RMSE
Avrami	$\ln[-\ln(1-X)] = \ln(k_A) + n \ln(t)$	$y = (0.99293 \pm 0.04724)x + (-5.16314 \pm 0.18341)$	$n = 0.99293 \pm 0.04724$ $k_A = 0.004765 \pm 0.006880$	0.995462	0.994453	0.063829	0.079893
SCM surface reaction	$1 - (1-X)^{1/3} = k_s t$	$y = (0.001565 \pm 0.000081)x + (0.006682 \pm 0.006)$	$k_s = 0.001565 \pm 0.000081$	0.993953	0.992744	0.000612	0.007457
SCM diffusion	$1 - 3(1-X)^{2/3} + 2(1-X) = k_d t$	$y = (0.001032 \pm 0.000123)x + (-0.016173 \pm 0.01)$	$k_d = 0.001032 \pm 0.000123$	0.968979	0.962775	0.001400	0.011283

Fig. 6. Linearized kinetic-model fits and corresponding residual distributions: (a) Avrami (JMAK), (b) SCM surface chemical reaction control, (c) SCM diffusion control, (d) Avrami residuals, and (e) SCM residuals. The Avrami and SCM surface-reaction models show good linearity, while the SCM diffusion model provides better agreement mainly at later stages of carbonation.

to verify the predictive behavior of the models in the original conversion domain. These results support the same overall trend, with the Avrami and SCM surface-reaction models providing better agreement than the SCM diffusion model.

This suggests that diffusion through a developing carbonate-silica product layer is unlikely to control the reaction from the beginning. Instead, diffusion through the developing carbonate-silica product layer may become increasingly relevant at advanced carbonation stages, based on the SCM diffusion trend together with the observed phase, crystallite-size, and microstructural evolution.

Collectively, the model fits support a multi-stage reaction mechanism. The SCM_{surface} reaction model is consistent with an interface-controlled dissolution step during much of the reaction progress where wollastonite dissolution supplies Ca²⁺ to the reactive boundary layer. The Avrami model describes the subsequent precipitation regime, during which CaCO₃ forms through nucleation and growth. The convergence of the Avrami exponent ($n \sim 1$) with the SCM-surface model suggests that the rate-limiting step is predominantly the chemical reaction at the phase boundary. At longer reaction times, the enhanced performance of the SCM_{diffusion} model is consistent with increasing transport resistance associated with the progressive development of carbonate-silica products, while surface-related processes remain dominant.

Independent structural and thermal analyses support this kinetic sequence. Time-resolved QXRD data reveal a progressive increase in calcite content and a corresponding decrease in wollastonite, consistent with a dissolution-precipitation mechanism. Additionally, the apparent calcite crystallite size increases with carbonation duration, suggesting ongoing carbonate development during the Avrami-governed stage. SEM/EDX analyses further support carbonate precipitation on a wollastonite-derived substrate, with Ca-rich rhombohedral domains forming as carbonation advances. In line with microstructural evolution, the $T(\text{DTG}_{\text{max}})$ (Fig. 5) shifts to higher values for more strongly carbonated products produced after a longer reaction time (i.e. 180 min). (e.g. 746.2°C for the lowest-carbonated sample after 5 min compared to 776.1°C for the highest-carbonated sample with the longest carbonation duration), indicating a more developed and thermally stable carbonate assemblage at higher conversion, which takes longer. Surface-property measurements also support the model-based interpretation: under favorable mass-transfer conditions, the specific surface area (SSA) remains relatively high, while under less favorable conditions, a greater decrease in SSA is consistent with earlier surface masking and pore-mouth occlusion, which may contribute to increasing transport limitations at later stages. These findings align with previous mechanistic studies. For instance, Daval et al. [19,23] demonstrated that under static or weakly mixed conditions, wollastonite carbonation remains

controlled by interfacial processes, and carbonate precipitation does not necessarily fill the fractured or porous silica-rich layer. This supports an initially interface-dominated regime before transport limitations become significant in certain microstructural contexts. In summary, the combined kinetic modeling and multi-technique characterization suggest that wet wollastonite carbonation is predominantly governed by surface-related dissolution–precipitation and carbonate nucleation and growth. The results further indicate that transport limitations may become increasingly relevant as carbonation products develop and the reaction progresses.

4. Conclusion and outlook

We demonstrated that operating conditions affect not only the degree of wollastonite carbonation but also the resulting product texture and CO₂-storage characteristics. The samples analyzed in this study were selected from a systematic screening phase of additive-free, mild wet carbonation, representing distinct carbonation outcomes. Multiple complementary characterization techniques were employed to develop a mechanistic interpretation of carbonation under these conditions. Specifically, XRD was used to monitor mineralogical evolution and carbonate crystallinity; SEM/EDX to resolve product-layer morphology and spatial elemental distributions; BET and skeletal density to quantify changes in accessible surface area and bulk transformation; and TGA/DTG to assess CO₂ release behavior and the apparent thermal stability of the carbonated phases.

The combined evidence supports a dissolution–precipitation pathway, wherein Ca²⁺ release from wollastonite is followed by CaCO₃ nucleation and growth. The precipitation mode appears to be strongly influenced by hydrodynamics and mass transport. QXRD shows progressive conversion of wollastonite into calcite under favorable conditions, while other silicate phases remain largely unchanged. Line-broadening analysis reveals an increase in apparent calcite crystallite size with increasing conversion and reaction progress, consistent with carbonate maturation as carbonation proceeds, as indicated by comparative crystallite sizes obtained using a consistent fitting protocol. SEM/EDX observations corroborate these findings: low-uptake conditions result in sparse, discontinuous Ca-rich rhombohedral precipitates on largely intact silicate grains, whereas high-uptake conditions produce abundant, coalescing carbonate domains that more extensively cover and bridge particles, reflecting a more developed carbonate–silica product texture. Changes in BET surface area and skeletal density are consistent with the corresponding microstructural transition from early surface masking and limited replacement to substantial mineral transformation. These trends align with the observed shift in T(DTG_{max}) to higher temperatures for more strongly carbonated products, suggesting a more stable and developed carbonate assemblage.

The novelty of this work lies in integrating phase, microstructural, surface, thermal, and kinetic observations to establish a coherent mechanistic interpretation of wollastonite wet carbonation under additive-free, mild conditions. The time-resolved kinetic study further supports this mechanistic framework. As carbonation duration increases, calcite content rises while wollastonite content declines, and carbonate crystallite size increases, indicating ongoing precipitation and growth throughout the reaction. The kinetic data are best described by an Avrami-type nucleation–growth model, which is consistent with an initial surface or interface-controlled stage, followed by a growth regime and a subsequent diffusion-influenced phase. This interpretation aligns with the observed microstructural and phase-evolution trends. Collectively, these results establish a coherent mechanistic basis for optimizing wollastonite carbonation by adjusting hydrodynamics and mass-transport conditions to maximize conversion and control product morphology and CO₂ storage stability.

Future work should include a dedicated kinetic study over a broader temperature range and reaction window to further resolve the relative contributions of surface reaction, nucleation–growth, and transport

limitations. Additional work should also (i) quantify amorphous Si-rich products and resolve the carbonate–silica layer architecture in more detail (e.g., internal-standard XRD/Rietveld and cross-sectional microscopy), (ii) verify pore-network evolution and pore-mouth occlusion with pore-size distribution measurements, and (iii) refine crystallite size/strain estimates using instrument-corrected line-broadening approaches.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Martin Rudolph: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Sahra Homae:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Doreen Ebert:** Investigation. **Robert Möckel:** Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jcou.2026.103504](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2026.103504).

Data Availability

The research data supporting this article have been deposited in the RODARE repository and are available at: <https://doi.org/10.14278/rodare.4693>.

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